

Asymptotic Properties of a Stochastic Predator-prey Model with Bedding-DeAngelis Functional Response

Authors : Xianqing Liu, Shouming Zhong, Lijiang Xiang

Abstract : Abstract—In this paper, a stochastic predator-prey system with Bedding-DeAngelis functional response is studied. By constructing a suitable Lyapunov function, sufficient conditions for species to be stochastically permanent is established. Meanwhile, we show that the species will become extinct with probability one if the noise is sufficiently large. In the end, some simulation figures are carried out to support the analytical findings.

Keywords : Stochastically permanent, extinct, white noise, Bedding-DeAngelis functional response

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